

FACTORS AFFECTING THE DEVELOPMENT OF EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITY OF FUTURE PRIMARY TEACHERS

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Abstract. Comments are presented on the problem of factors influencing the development of educational activities of future primary school teachers. The article presents scientific opinions on external and internal factors in the development of cognitive activity of primary school teachers and factors for the effective implementation of this activity. The article uses the scientific theories of a number of psychologists and teachers.

Key words: primary school teacher, cognitive process, external factors, internal factors, educational process, cognitive activity.

ФАКТОРЫ, ВЛИЯЮЩИЕ НА РАЗВИТИЕ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ НАЧАЛЬНЫХ УСЛОВИЙ

Аннотация. Представлены комментарии к проблеме факторов, влияющих на развитие учебной деятельности будущих учителей начальных классов. В статье представлены научные мнения о внешних и внутренних факторах развития познавательной деятельности учителей начальных классов и факторах эффективного осуществления этой деятельности. В статье использованы научные теории ряда психологов и педагогов.

Ключевые слова: учитель начальных классов, познавательный процесс, внешние факторы, внутренние факторы, учебный процесс, познавательная деятельность.

External and internal factors aimed at improving the quality and efficiency of intellectual development of future primary school teachers can be shown. Scientists include psychological characteristics in the group of internal factors: motives, hobbies, interests that occupy a leading place in the personality structure, orientation, character, feelings, abilities, intellectual processes, etc. The group of external factors includes the conditions in which activities are carried out.

For example, G. Rosenfeld identified the following content factors of reading motivation:

1. Studying without pleasure from the lesson or without interest in the subject being taught;

2. Education without personal interests and interests;

3. Training on social identification;

4. Learning for success or fear of failure; 5. Compulsory or compulsory training;

6. Education based on concepts and moral obligations or recognized standards;

7. Learning to achieve goals in everyday life;

8. Based on social goals, demands and values.

J. Bruner takes a different approach to the issue of learning motivation. It recognizes the empirical and theoretical conditions that influence the effectiveness of creative communication that occurs during the learning process. J. Bruner always thinks not only about the motivating and perceived factors of the learning process, but also about the reasons for learning. This is, first of all, the importance of reasons in the nature of cognition in the process of reading and the placement of emotional issues of internal patience that arise when learning something new. It should be said that this inner patience is combined with positive motivation aimed at developing emotional learning and knowledge. The role of the internal factor in the development of the tendency to master complex educational material is great. For example, the more complex and logical a topic is, the more intellectual “stimulation” it must receive in order to begin studying the next complex topic with sufficient interest.

In the system of psychoanalytic views, the decisive factor is the division of the origin of the motives of cognition and understanding into internal (innate) or external (later acquired) causes. For example, E. Desi defines factors as causes inherent in human birth, i.e. congenital. In order for future primary school teachers to become mature cadres, a psychological and pedagogical environment is needed that develops educational activities aimed at a specific goal. To satisfy one’s personal-reflective and personal-motivational needs in organizing the process of development of educational and cognitive activity, a proportional adaptation of educational goals to the content of education is carried out according to dynamic models of the pedagogical and psychological environment, which is multifaceted and rich. In diverse motivation it is necessary to have motivation, strength, and the ability to stimulate intensive development of abilities and cognitive activity.

In this regard, P. Ya. Galperin’s theory about the gradual composition of a student’s intellectual development and improving the quality and effectiveness of educational activities is of interest. This theory was developed on the basis of ideas and thoughts about the process of cognitive development by A. N. Leontiev. According to this theory, during human ontogenesis,

activity is internalized and a process of gradual transformation of external activity into internal cognitive activity occurs. Therefore, the effectiveness of identifying small opportunities and implementing them depends on personal motivation. The mental process of intellectual development cannot be realized without personal reflex, volitional and emotional efforts to develop educational activities.

The approach based on the development of educational activities involves the implementation of the following educational directions: cognitive, motivational, acquiring skills in the practical use of acquired knowledge in solving problems; formation of educational competencies, implementation of practical situations in the educational process. This also implies the presence of methods and means of receiving, processing and transmitting information.

In this sense, there must be intellectual development of future primary school teachers, as well as the necessary knowledge and skills, personal reflexive and personal motivation to improve the quality and efficiency of the process of educational and cognitive activity. To support the internal development of a future primary school teacher, the educational process must correspond to the active level of educational material, development, and this level must exceed existing knowledge in complexity. Otherwise he will be deprived of development.

If the tasks recommended for a future primary school teacher are equated with cognitive ability, then these forces will not motivate him to further develop cognitive activity. To do this, questions are used aimed at mastering educational tasks and materials by using the power of knowledge and intellectual activity. From here, the mediating role of the teacher in understanding educational tasks and questions aimed at mastering educational material becomes clear. It is the methods associated with understanding that help the teacher teach educational materials. The educational activity management system is determined using educational materials that future primary school teachers must master in the course of methodological developments.

At the same time, if we take into account the ideas, aspirations and motivations of those who develop their inner strength, if they are asked questions related to the topic, then they will be carried out on the basis of previously existing knowledge.

Thus, based on the opinion of scientists, we advocate understanding the process of personal-reflective and personal-motivational development of educational and cognitive activity as a factor in the integrative coordination of the educational-cognitive trajectory with the vector functions of educational goals.

A number of scientists classify the reasons for the development of educational activity according to its essence and methods of understanding. Depending on the various needs in the development of educational activities, motives are divided into biological and social types. Social

motives are divided into types such as self-esteem, self-expression, achieving success, the pursuit of knowledge, and avoiding failures. Another direction in the classification of motives can be divided into creative communication, study, sports and other social motives according to the type of activity exhibited by the student. Here the name of the reason is determined by the type of activity.

N.I.Khalilova and F.I.Khaidarov in their scientific research expressed the factors that increase the quality and efficiency of intellectual development and educational activities as follows.

Factors that increase the quality and effectiveness of educational activities:

Subjective – manager status, individual characteristics, level of training.

Object - environment - living conditions, objective conditions of the situation, organization of activities, organization of the workplace, information flow, control of activities.

Thus, the data presented indicate that the role of factors in activating educational knowledge is great. This, in turn, is one of the important factors in the development of socio-psychological and pedagogical sciences.

In the course of our research, in order to determine the connection between the development of social perception and the leading motives for the educational activities of future primary school teachers, we carried out “Motivation for studying at a university”, proposed by T.I. Ilyin. with the subjects. In the research methodology, the indicator of future primary school teachers of the 4th grade included the following information about the motives for the development of educational activities, knowledge and obtaining a diploma for future primary school teachers of the 4th grade. Year 1 showed that it was relatively high. For future primary school teachers, the average arithmetic value of motivation for learning is 32.3, factors for the development of educational activities - 37.6, desire to obtain a diploma - 30.1.

Mathematics is a compulsory subject for the training of future primary school teachers using a competency-based approach. Features of the content of this topic are large volumes, high labor intensity, and difficulty of mastering. However, knowledge of the importance of mathematics and sufficient personal motivational focus can help solve this problem.

Personal motivational orientation is understood as “a set of internal and external driving forces that encourage a person to work, determine the limits and forms of work, and increase attention to this work aimed at achieving certain goals”.

The personal and motivational component of future primary school teachers determines the emergence, direction, methods of implementation and results of a particular activity. Personal motivational training is understood as a system of motivations and human needs, manifested in a

positive attitude towards educational activities, especially towards its aspects directly related to education.

Practice shows that the stage-by-stage preparation of future primary school teachers for information exchange activities in the process of empirical and theoretical training does not show a high level of internal and external driving forces; psychological and pedagogical tools are very necessary.

In training programs for future primary school teachers, cognitive, affective and psychomotor educational goals, which form the basis of the knowledge necessary for the harmonious development of the teacher's personality in all aspects, can be proportionally adapted to the content of education.

At the same time, in addition to basic knowledge and skills, the education of a personal-reflective and personal-motivational trajectory of orientation is necessary for the formation of the qualities necessary for future primary school teachers in order for them to become psychologists capable of overcoming all difficulties. Educational activity develops on the basis of integrative coordination with vector functions of goals.

Currently, a sufficient amount of research is being conducted on the use of methods of teaching mathematics and the use of pedagogical technologies in the educational process, which helps to increase the efficiency of the educational process. However, the issues of psychological characteristics of the effectiveness of creative communication in teaching mathematics have not been studied enough. Based on this, in the process of teaching mathematics, it was determined that it is necessary to study the development of conceptual aspects of relations between subjects of interaction and step-by-step learning within the framework of the activity approach.

Mathematics is a natural science and its purpose is to instill methods of collecting mathematical information, finding new possibilities and representing them. Future primary school teachers must know the basics of mathematical analysis, algebra and geometry, probability theory, mathematical statistics, be able to use mathematical language and symbols in professional activities, and solve mathematical problems.

Psychological and pedagogical analysis conducted to study the characteristics of the educational process and educational activities of future primary school teachers showed that teaching mathematics is based on active intellectual activity. In the course of training, intellectual activity develops, which creates the basis for theoretical thinking and mental processes of knowledge of related sciences.

In the process of teaching mathematics, the goal is to educate future primary school teachers through personal-reflective and personal-motivational orientation, the formation of their

cognitive, affective and psychomotor spheres. Knowledge is aimed at improving the quality and efficiency of activities and depends on its development.

The conducted studies show that the factor influencing the development of educational activity depends on the personal-reflective and personal-motivational level. The solution to this problem is developmental training in step-by-step preparation for information exchange activities.

To implement it, it is necessary to formulate tasks for complexity and dynamic models of logically developing educational activities in mathematics. When presenting theoretical material in lectures, as well as in practical classes, the influence on the development of educational activities is determined by solving problems of proportional coordination of cognitive, affective and psychomotor learning goals with the content of learning based on integrative coordination of vector functions of educational goals. Mathematical abilities depend on cognitive and intellectual abilities based on integrative coordination with vector functions of the development of educational activity in the process of solving mathematical problems.

Some future primary school teachers cannot demonstrate mathematical ability, so important factors in teaching are communicative, academic, cognitive, professional, social motivation, as well as the development of educational activities and learning. Motives for avoiding self-awareness are formed. In the process of teaching mathematics, an integral part of educational activities is the training of the future primary school teacher, the formation of his motivational field.

It is possible to improve the educational activities of higher school teachers through the development of the educational process, personality and intellectual abilities of future primary school teachers. Based on the results obtained, the study of the relationship between mathematical, intellectual abilities and motivation allows us to draw a number of conclusions. Based on the Pearson correlation coefficient, which showed the presence of correlation matrices between motives and mathematical abilities, significant (significance less than 0.01) correlations were identified between the following motives: communicative, reputational, professional, creative, educational, cognitive and social.

Correlation analysis was also used to determine correlations between various test indicators (significance less than 0.05): between the ability to solve theoretical and practical mathematical problems, spatial generalization, attention and memory; as well as reasoning, verbal analogies and generalizations; spatial thinking, practical and theoretical problem solving skills; verbal thinking and verbal analogies; attention, memory and all mathematical abilities.

Based on the analysis of the teacher's personal-reflective and personal-motivational factors, the following factors influencing the development of educational and cognitive activity were grouped:

“cognitive-motivational”, educational, creative motive. This factor is determined by the interdependence of cognitive motives, which is characterized by other methods and without repetition. When interpreting the results, future elementary school teachers who want to develop educational activities are distinguished by their desire for creativity and self-awareness;

A factor influencing the development of educational and cognitive activity is mathematical abilities, which include the ability to solve theoretical mathematical problems. This factor includes practical abilities to solve mathematical problems, spatial generalization and imagination, memory, and attention. If a future primary school teacher has a good memory and attention, he will quickly remember the necessary formulas and will not make mistakes, which, in turn, will help him solve assigned non-standard problems, affects his abilities and leads to good mastery of mathematics.

A factor influencing the development of educational activities is the effectiveness of creative communication, that is, verbal thinking, verbal analogies, and verbal generalization. This creative communication is a heuristic conversation that is highly effective. The results of the study confirmed the relationship between the components of speech thinking among future primary school teachers; Factors influencing the development of learning activities include verbal analogies, thinking and social motives. Prospective elementary school teachers with a high level of verbal thinking will be able to make verbal analogies more easily and at the same time will be less inclined to explain their thoughts.

Identification and analysis of factors influencing the development of educational and cognitive activity made it possible to clarify the psychological characteristics of teaching mathematics and divide them into general and specific characteristics. Common traits help develop a combination of math and verbal skills, as well as motivation to learn and cognitive functioning.

Pedagogical heritage is one of the important methodological factors of future primary school teachers in the process of development of educational activities. Потому что был воплощен моральный, духовный и физически зрелый опыт молодого поколения. In this matter, it is important to pay attention to the following: Akhmat Fargani, Abu Nasr ibn Iraq, Musa Khorezmi, Mirza Ulugbek, scientific achievements in the field of mathematics, algebra, astronomy and trigonometry are identified with the scientific and theoretical foundations of the development of learning and knowledge.

The views of Abu Rayhan Beruni and Abu Nasr Farabi are a practical factor in the formation of educational activities.

Also factors in the process of organizing cognitive activity are interest in learning, educational goals, emotions, personal anxiety and emotional stability, the need to achieve achievements and creative communication; intellectual abilities and openness to creative communication; spoke about personal experience and skills.

Effective development of the personal experience of a future primary school teacher is ensured by the implementation of the following pedagogical conditions: regular study of the personal experience of a future primary school teacher in the field of life plans; consistent organization of situations for the development of his personal experience of educational activities; the use of heuristic teaching methods as a means of implementing situations in the development of personal experience of a future primary school teacher.

Therefore, the process of formation and development of personal experience of the subject of educational activity of the future primary school teacher will continue only individually. The personal level of a person's consciousness is a deeply intimate area of his psyche. Personality development manifests itself in an individual as a peculiar construction of his internal, predominantly intimate world, into which no one can interfere. The only thing that can be done in educational settings is the creation of creative communication.

Also, the components of the educational activity of future primary school teachers are closely related to personal-reflective, i.e., the personal-mental, emotional-evaluative activity of the teacher. This form of understanding the inner world of a person is aimed at analyzing the important components of the personality: goals and ideals, abilities and capabilities, motives and needs. Logical reasoning is the most reasonable form, focused on cognitive processes and associated with the analysis and assessment of the characteristics of thinking, attention and memory. One of the components of educational activity is personal-motivational. This is an impulse to action.

Motivation also refers to a person's ability to effectively and actively satisfy their needs.

In psychology, personal motivation is a dynamic process that includes psychophysiological mechanisms that control the teacher's behavior and determine its stability, direction, organization and activity.

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